

PRACTICAL WORKS IN THE SYSTEM OF METHODS OF TEACHING
NATURAL (SCIENTIFIC) SCIENCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8153336>

Annotation. Practical work plays a large role in mastering the knowledge of nature. Practical work is a method of teaching students to various labor operas in the process of their activities. Practical work complements observation and experiments, teaches children to work creatively together in the study of natural material. Practical work makes it possible to comprehensively consolidate the knowledge gained in the course of the lesson, on excursions. In addition, practical work contributes to the formation of Labor qualifications and skills in children, independent work. In the article.various teaching methods are also outlined in the practice of teaching natural (SCIENCE) subjects.

Keywords: Natural (SCIENCE) Sciences, method and styles, herbarium, compilation of collections, mulyaj, layout, indiviudal.

Practical work plays an important role in acquiring knowledge about nature. Practical work is a method of teaching students various labor operations in the course of their activities.

In the studies of A. S. Lysenko, practical work includes such activities as collecting natural material during excursions, caring for plants in the school grounds and in a corner of wildlife, creating herbariums and collections, making models, models and visual aids. It is explained that the implementation of these works helps the teacher to increase the cognitive activity of students, concretize and consolidate knowledge [2].

In the first grade, children have not yet mastered the skills of practical work. Therefore, at the beginning, practical work will be in the nature of training. For example, to learn how to determine the length of the shadow of a stake at noon (midday) or measure the temperature of the air and record their results, it will take a lot of practice.Students gradually move from simple tasks that do not require much time and effort to more complex tasks. Practical work should become more and more independent over time.

The manner in which the teacher conducts practical work should also change: if in the first lessons it is necessary to instruct each student in detail in steps, then in the second half of the year it is enough to instruct all students in the class on the work. . When conducting practical work, the teacher must

determine the level of knowledge on which students rely. All experiments and practical work should be carried out with records that must be entered in the "Book of Daily Observations". It is also recommended to draw pictures, paste objects into plasticine, model natural materials. In this case, students carefully look at the depicted object or event, notice features that were previously ignored.

E. S. Gladkaya, writing down conclusions during practical work or making notes under the pictures, helps children clarify definitions and remember the terms of natural science. Practical work should be carried out in connection with experience and observations. For example, he explains that before observing the temperature of water as it heats up and cools down, students need to learn about the three states of water and the transition between them as the temperature changes [1].

Students should be familiar with the thermometer and be able to use it. In order for them to be able to freely use the knowledge gained in grade 2, the teacher first conducts a conversation, then practical work, at which time he repeats the necessary experiments and offers to look at the thermometer. It is necessary to apply existing knowledge, skills and abilities to previous experience, as this increases the mental activity of students, helps to better assimilate new knowledge.

Practical work in the classroom. In the classroom, practical exercises are held with handouts that give students the opportunity to receive what is being studied by several senses, that is, they not only see the object, but also conduct various experiments on it, its properties (for example, by trying, hitting with a hammer, they check the fragility of things, their elasticity, flexibility, etc.) by bending. In SCIENCE lessons, inanimate and animate objects of nature (stones, beneficial insects, plants and their parts, small animals, etc.) are used as handouts. Practical work is carried out in the following order: announcement of the purpose of the work; teacher guidance; explanation of the task; distribution of materials; observation; explanation of the results of the work done - interview; writing conclusions in a notebook; drawing pictures. During practical work, the teacher helps some students when the task seems incomprehensible or difficult. If necessary, it is necessary to repeatedly explain the content of the work as a whole. The main difficulty of practical work is to understand the observed phenomena, highlight the most important of them and be able to formulate conclusions.

Practical classes in the field of wildlife are associated with long-term observations and experiments. In a lesson devoted to practical work in a corner of wildlife, its purpose and sequence of implementation should be explained.

Students can ask questions. The results of work in the corner of nature are used in the study of topical topics. In the course of practical work, the teacher observes the students, gives additional explanations, evaluates the quality of the work, marks the good ones, and suggests eliminating the mistakes made. The lesson ends with a final conversation: it is determined what new information the children learned, what they learned to do, how they behaved during work.

At the end, the educator gives information on how to care for the planted seeds or planted plants, how this work is organized.

Practical work on excursions. During the excursions, much attention is paid to independent work on the instructions of the educator (collecting leaves, pruning dry branches, drawing, taking measurements, making a collection of minerals, etc.).

Before doing the work, students receive tasks from the teacher, who introduces the students to the method of work (for example, how to collect leaves, how to cut branches, how to dig up plants).

In excursions, as well as in work before school, the teacher helps children using various methodological techniques.

Thus, depending on the purpose and content of the lesson, the teacher uses different teaching methods and styles. Whatever methods and techniques the teacher chooses, their comprehensive, complementary use should serve the main goal - improving the perception of natural objects and phenomena by children and the correct formation of concepts about natural science (SCIENCE).

Experiments are often carried out in the study of physiological processes. Experiments are long-term and short-term. A common example of a short-term experiment or experiment done in science and botany classes is the study of seed composition, the physical properties of soil, the formation of starch in a leaf, and the like. Students perform much simpler experiments at home, such as the conditions for seed germination, the evaporation of water from leaves. Typically, students perform experimental work as an extracurricular activity (individual and group) in the school's wildlife corner or study corner.

Practical work complements observations and experiments, teaches children to work together on the study of natural material. Practical work allows you to comprehensively consolidate the knowledge gained during the lesson and

excursion. In addition, practical work helps children develop labor skills and abilities, work independently.

It is known that the methods chosen in accordance with the content and age of the students provide a high quality of knowledge. A method is, in a general sense, a way to achieve a goal. Teaching method is how the teacher transmits knowledge and at the same time receives it from students.

This definition of the method represents its two interrelated sides: the teacher, the giver, the influencer, and the student, the receiver, the learner.

The nature of this interaction depends on the source of knowledge. The source of knowledge is determined by the content of the educational material, which is the leading one in the educational process.

In the practice of teaching natural science (SCIENCE), various teaching methods have developed. However, depending on these more important features, they can be grouped as follows:

resources from which students learn;

the nature of student activities;

the nature of the activity of students in the educational process.

These three characteristics stem from understanding teaching and learning as a holistic process. In this case, the activities of the teacher (teacher) and the student (student) are interconnected and necessary, and the sources of knowledge are closely related to the activities of the teacher.

In the classroom, the teacher uses different teaching methods. When choosing teaching methods, a number of factors are important: the development of an auxiliary school at the present stage, the subject of study, the content of the material being studied, the level of preparation of students for the assimilation of educational material. The nature of the choice of style and its application is determined not only by the purpose of the educational material in the lesson, but also by the content. The concept of learning style is one of the basic concepts of didactics and methodology.

Teaching in pedagogy means the joint activity of teachers and students, understanding the methods of work. With the help of this activity, the teacher transfers knowledge, students expand their knowledge, develop cognitive abilities, develop their worldview.

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